

Hexavalent chromium dual water remediation and sensing based on hybrid polymer/metal-organic framework composites

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Chromium
Metal-organic frameworks
Multifunctional composite membranes
Potable-analytical systems
Water remediation

ABSTRACT

The environment contains numerous chemical pollutants from natural processes and human activities, including pesticides, pharmaceuticals, and industrial chemicals. Specifically, the issue of hexavalent chromium water pollution, whether from natural or industrial sources, remains a global and unresolved threat. Hence, there is a need for efficient and prompt monitoring of Cr(VI) concentration in water to determine the potential danger and to facilitate the development of efficient remediation strategies. In this work, the metal-organic framework (MOF) UiO-66-NH₂ was immobilized into poly (vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) (PVDF-HFP) polymeric membranes, manufactured in different morphologies, to act as Cr(VI) sorbent to develop a novel portable, easily reactivable, and reusable water filtering and sensing technology. The multifunctional membranes demonstrated an adsorption capacity of 2.32 mg/L in 300 minutes for plasma electrospun-oriented fiber membranes with 10 % w/v of MOFs. The most efficient morphology was selected and integrated into a portable system for simultaneous detection and adsorption in a short time. It shows approximately 50 % adsorption efficiency and a colorimetric sensitivity with an excellent determination coefficient R² of 0.990, even for very low concentrations at 0.085 ppm. To the best of our knowledge, this work presents the first system that utilizes multi-structured active materials for the remediation and monitoring of an aquatic contaminant.

1. Introduction

Environmental water pollution is a prevailing global issue that has short to long-term detrimental consequences on the health and welfare of the ecosystems. As modern industrial activities intensify and diversify, water pollution becomes increasingly complex. Pesticides, phenolic compounds, fluorinated persistent chemicals, heavy metals, and other substances are increasingly detected in surface and underground water sources, either individually or forming highly risky cocktails with unpredictable ecological impacts [1]. Today, a quarter of the world's population accesses drinking water from unsafe or polluted sources, painting a concerning global picture [2].

Hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) is an inorganic pollutant that exemplifies the aforementioned global concern. Its solubility in water renders Cr(VI) a highly mobile oxyanion capable of travelling long distances from its source of origin. The correlation between the oxidation state of chromium and its environmental and health hazards is noteworthy [3]. Toxicity and ecotoxicity, bio-persistence, carcinogenicity, and environmental mobility of Cr(VI) exceeds by far those observed in Cr(III) [4]. Consequently, world environmental protection Agencies, such as the U. S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) or The United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), classify Cr(VI) as one of the highest-priority hazardous pollutants [5,6].

Included within the family of heavy metals, Cr(VI) can be found

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2024.113839>

Received 21 May 2024; Received in revised form 15 July 2024; Accepted 13 August 2024

Available online 15 August 2024

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naturally in water sources, but most of the time, its entrance into the environment arises from industrial activities such as mining, leathering or metal plating [7,8]. The use of hexavalent chromium for these purposes presents a multifaceted problem. In several cases, industries employ highly concentrated chromium baths, creating hazardous working environments requiring strict safety regulations [9]. Secondly, treating these baths once they're exhausted is not straightforward. Chemical reduction of Cr(VI) to the less harmful Cr(III) is one of the most commonly applied solutions to mitigate this environmental problem. However, this process can still result in industrial wastewater with chromium concentrations well above legal thresholds. Thus, any release to the environment supposes an additional increase of the background pollution in the surrounding media. To give a relevant example, today, 75 % of U.S. drinking water, and hence, over 200 million Americans are at risk of unsafe exposure to hexavalent chromium [10].

Early detection and removal of chromium are of utmost importance for several reasons. Firstly, it aids in preventing workplace risks. Secondly, it helps in assessing whether industrial wastewater, once exhausted and treated, complies with legal chromium concentrations or requires further processing. Lastly, it is crucial for removing and sensing chromium once it enters surface or groundwater streams [11]. In all these scenarios, cost-effective, reliable, and reusable chromium treatment and sensing technologies are essential for controlling chromium concentrations in the surrounding environment [11]. Additionally, they are critical in mitigating any risks associated with chromium if detected. Further, portable technologies are relevant in isolated regions with limited resources or in the aftermath of a natural calamity. In these scenarios, having access to affordable and user-friendly gadgets that provide insights about the potability of water could be crucial for saving human lives [12].

In terms of hexavalent chromium removal or immobilization, Cr(VI) is usually extracted from water by co-precipitation, reverse osmosis [13], ion exchange, membrane filtration [14], coagulation, and flocculation [15]. Every technical solution has advantages and disadvantages depending on the application scenario. In general, they all come with expensive operational costs, sensitivity to pH levels, and, most significantly, inefficiency in reducing Cr(VI) concentrations below legally acceptable limits in specific operating situations [16]. Most importantly, in the scope of the present work, their portability is still quite limited. Specific adsorption presents a more environmentally friendly and portable technology to apply for addressing water contamination caused by Cr(VI) [17,18]. Effective sorbents should possess high selectivity and efficiency and be easily processed, maintained, applied and reactivated. In parallel, they can be packed in columns or integrated into membranes that can be used as portable devices [19,20]. An optimal adsorption process is inherently related to the affinity and density of adsorption sites for Cr(VI) anions into the sorbent. Following these two criteria, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) porous materials stand out from classic sorbents. First, MOFs exhibit porous crystal structures with record surface areas and second, their frameworks can be encoded with specific chemical groups to capture chromium oxyanions in different scenarios [6]. Research on MOFs highlights their potential for water sensing and contaminant removal, but also reveals some limitations, especially on their water stability and adsorption selectivity [21]. The strategies for the design of water stable MOFs are well established, being in that respect the ones based on Zr(IV) and Ti(IV) relatively stable in the short to midterm to the exposure to water, and even for some of them to acidic conditions. Further, the application of these porous materials for water remediation limits the selection of their components to environmentally friendly metal ions (i.e. Fe(III) – Ti(IV) > Al(III) ~ Zr(IV) ~ Cr(III)) and organic linkers [22]. The last point is of special concern, since the encoding of different functional groups in the organic building units of MOFs, such as amino, carboxyl, and sulfonic acid groups, opens the room to a certain extent to control the selectivity and adsorption capacity [23]. This is especially effective for the capture of anionic species as chromate anions, where the installation of positively charged groups

can modulate both their photoreduction and capture efficiency [24]. Selective adsorption is the first step for the subsequent sensing of the metals. Thus the capture of chromium ions is usually related to the monitoring of a variation in a physic-chemical property of the MOFs; which in most cases is the enhancement or the quenching of a colorimetric or luminescence signal arising from the organic or inorganic components of the framework [25,26].

While Cr(VI) remediation and adsorption technologies are well developed, the simultaneous combination of these technologies with portable and affordable sensors that enable real-time measurements in different scenarios requires more research [27,28]. Portable sensors already exist for various applications, such as biomedicine, [29,30], food engineering [31], energy systems [32] and environmental management [33–35]. When portability is taking into consideration colorimetric [36] or electrochemical sensors implemented by printing technologies (i.e., such as screen-printing [37], or wax printing [38, 39]), polymeric substrates are a highly appealing alternative. Nevertheless, for hexavalent chromium, most of the detection protocols are far from portable technologies. To mention the most relevant ones, the quantification of chromium concentration in water usually involves High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) [40], ion chromatography (IC) [41], X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) [42], or UV-Vis analysis after complexation with diphenyl carbazide (DPC) [43]. Thus, developing a portable-printed colorimetric sensor for chromium would represent a breakthrough compared to the current state of the art.

This work introduces a novel, avant-garde approach in which a multifunctional portable-printed system integrates a remediation and sensing solution. This portable system can simultaneously measure chromium concentration in water samples using colorimetry and carry out remediation to levels that meet the safety standards set by the World Health Organization (WHO). To optimize remediation and sensing performance, poly (vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene), PVDF-HFP, has been employed as a robust matrix to integrate Metal-Organic Framework particles able to capture and sense by colorimetry Cr(VI). PVDF-HFP is a fluorinated polymer with outstanding chemical, thermal, mechanical and radiation resistance [44].

The PVDF-HFP matrix has been combined with an amino functionalized zirconium-based MOF (i.e. UiO-66-NH₂) to obtain a composite system that has demonstrated efficacy in capturing and separating both inorganic and organic contaminants [20]. PVDF-HFP@UiO-66-NH₂ composite membranes have been processed in a variety of different morphologies from (i) oriented and (ii) randomly-oriented electrospun fibres, as well as (iii) porous membranes obtained via thermally induced phase separation technique (TIPS). UiO-66-NH₂ has been selected as an active component because it has already been proven as an outstanding adsorbent and photocatalyst for chromate oxyanions [24,36]. In parallel, its chemical stability, even in aqueous and acidic environments, ensures its robustness and longevity in practical applications such as water remediation [45]. Furthermore, to overcome the hydrophobicity of the membranes, surface post-treatments with oxygen plasma were performed, which introduce morphological modifications and/or functional groups into the surface of the material [46].

These PVDF-HFP/MOF composite platforms were designed and tested for holds the ability to remediate and quantify chromium in water. This represents the first example of a portable system that integrates detection and remediation simultaneously, a feature with significant potential for diverse environmental applications.

2. Experimental procedure

2.1. Materials

Poly (vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) (PVDF-HFP, SOLEF® 21,216/1001) was purchased from Solvay, with an HFP content of 12 % and a molecular weight of 600.000 g/mol. Polylactide acid filament (PLA) was purchased from Prusa Research (Prague, Czech

Republic). N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF, $\geq 99\%$), potassium dichromate ($K_2Cr_2O_7$), 1,5-Diphenyl carbazide and amino terephthalic acid (BDC BDC-NH₂ 99%) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. Milli-Q ultrapure water was also used. Zirconium (IV) chloride 99.5% was purchased from Alfa Aesar.

2.2. Synthesis of MOF UiO-66-NH₂

The synthesis of UiO-66-NH₂ was conducted using a solvothermal method, resulting in a particle size distribution tightly centered at a diameter of 300 nm. A solution was prepared by dissolving 34.9 mg of zirconium chloride in 10 mL of acetic acid: N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF) (33:66 v/v) with continuous stirring in a Pyrex® autoclave. Subsequently, a solution of zirconium chloride was subjected to the dropwise addition of 2-amino terephthalic acid (24.9 mg). The reactor was subjected to isothermal conditions within a Thermo Scientific Heratherm Heating and Drying Advanced Protocol Ovens at a temperature of 120 °C for 12 hours. The material was retrieved through centrifugation using a Hettich EBA21 centrifuge at 6500 revolutions per minute for 15 minutes. It was then washed with 50 mL of DMF and two washes with 50 mL of methanol. Subsequently, the material was washed twice with a 0.1 M cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) solution, each time using 50 mL. Finally, the material was dried at 80 °C overnight.

2.3. PVDF-HFP based membranes production

2.3.1. Membranes preparation

The following methods were followed to prepare the solutions of PVDF-HFP and PVDF-HFP@MOFs. For pristine membranes, 1 g of PVDF-HFP was magnetically stirred in 9 mL of DMF until the polymer wholly dissolved. For the composite membranes (CM), first, 0.111 g of MOF nanoparticles were first dispersed in 9 mL of DMF to achieve a final mass ratio of 10% for UiO-66-NH₂/PVDF-HFP. The MOF loading into the membrane was selected based on previous investigations in chromium remediation with composite PVDF-HFP based membranes [6]. This process was carried out at room temperature in an ultrasonic bath (Fisherbrand FB15056) for 2 hours. PVDF-HFP was added to the mixture to achieve a PVDF-HFP/DMF ratio of 10:90 v/v. Finally, the mixture was stirred magnetically until the polymer completely dissolved.

For thermally induced phase separation (TIPS) prepared membranes, the solution/dispersion was poured into a clean glass Petri dish and left to evaporated at room temperature for about two weeks. The slow solvent evaporation leads to the formation of large pores in the PVDF-HFP structure. The thickness of the TIPS membranes was 410.6 ± 7.3 μ m.

For the electrospun membranes, the solution was poured into 10 mL disposable syringes and were placed into a syringe pump (New Era NE-1000). The syringes were equipped with a blunt steel needle with an inner diameter of 500 μ m. The solution was pumped with a flow rate of 0.5 mL/h during electrospinning using a high-voltage power supply (Glassman PS/FC30P04) set at 15 kV. Randomly oriented electrospun membranes were collected on a grounded 20 \times 15 cm static aluminium plate collector that was positioned 15 cm distant from the needle.

Oriented electrospun membranes were obtained by the same procedure, but the fibers were collected on a grounded rotating drum collector at a rotation speed of 1500 rpm.

2.3.2. Membranes Surface modification by plasma treatment

PVDF and its copolymers have intrinsic hydrophobic characteristics that limit their application as substrates in portable analytical devices [46]. Plasma treatment was applied to all membranes to create superhydrophilic membranes. The appropriate selection of the plasma environment (O₂, Ar, N₂, or other), treatment time, and applied power are all related to the effectiveness of plasma treatment. One of the most reactive elements, oxygen, leads to hydrophilic carboxyl groups on the surface of polymers, thereby reducing their hydrophobicity [47]. Thus, Samples

were surface-treated in a plasma chamber (Diener Electronics Zepto) with a 40 kHz radio frequency plasma generator. Before applying the plasma, the base pressure was 20 Pa. Following that, oxygen was used to create a 100 W plasma for 10 min at an overall pressure of 80 Pa. These parameters were established in previous research [46]. The oxygen plasma-treated and untreated processed membranes will be denoted as w/ and w/o plasma.

In the following, the prepared membranes will be identified as indicated in Table 1. It is to notice that TIPS, OF and ROF refer to thermally induced phase separation, oriented electrospun and randomly oriented electrospun processed membranes, respectively.

2.4. Design and development of handheld device

The sensor's three-dimensional structure was fabricated using a 3D Fused deposition modelling (FDM) printing technique. This structure serves the dual purpose of supporting the filtration and detection membrane and acting as a reservoir for the filtered solution. Specifically, a Prusa i3 MK3 printer was employed to fabricate the structure using polylactic acid (PLA) material (1.75 mm EasyFil PLA). The geometrical characteristics of the system are shown in Figure Fig. 1-i).

The different membranes were cut into circles with a diameter of 12 mm and inserted between two-layer supports, one of laminated plastic and one of adhesive plastic. The final device has small dimensions (30x25x25 mm), so several can be easily transported and used in remote locations (Fig. 1-iii).

2.5. UiO-66-NH₂ characterization

The MOF nanoparticles were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), thermogravimetric (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and infrared spectroscopy (IR) before and after activating the samples at 150 °C.

The crystallinity and phase purity of the UiO-66-NH₂ sample after being washed and activated were evaluated by X-ray powder diffraction (PXRD). The patterns were measured at room temperature using a Panalytical Xpert CuK α diffractometer in the following conditions: 2 θ range = 5–70°, step size = 0.05°, exposure time = 10 s per step. Full peak fit profile matching of the patterns was performed further to assess the crystallinity and purity of the sample. The final fitting is shown in Figure S1, supplementary information. The morphology of the synthesized UiO-66-NH₂ was observed by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) (JEOL JSM-7000 F) operating at 10 kV.

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra were measured using a Jasco FT/IR-6100 spectrometer in the ATR mode (FTIR-ATR). To this end, the MOF sample was diluted in KBr to 1% wt.

Table 1

Identification of the membranes, indicating filler content, processing method and plasma treatment. Thus, 10%TIPS-P identifies a composite membrane with 10 wt% filler content prepared by thermally induced phase separation (TIPS) and with plasma treatment (P).

	wt% of MOF UiO-66-NH ₂	PLASMA TREATMENT	DESIGNATION
TIPS MEMBRANES	-	w/.P	TIPS-P
	-	wo/.P	TIPS
	10 wt%	w/.P	10 %TIPS-P
	10 wt%	wo/.P	10 %TIPS
ORIENTED ELECTROSPUN FIBERS	-	w/.P	OF-P
	-	wo/.P	OF
RANDOMLY ORIENTED ELECTROSPUN FIBERS	10 wt%	w/.P	10 %OF-P
	10 wt%	wo/.P	10 %OF
	-	w/.P	ROF
	-	wo/.P	ROF-P
	10 wt%	w/.P	10 %ROF-P
	10 wt%	wo/.P	10 %ROF

Fig. 1. - i) FDM 3D printing process of the PLLA reservoir and the device assembly with the insertion of the multifunctional membrane between a two-layer support. ii) Dimensions of the final portable sensing 3D device compared to a 2 euros coin.

KBr pellets of 13 mm in diameter were performed by pressing the powdered KBr/MOF mixture under 10 tonnes pressure for a minute. Each spectrum was recorded from 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} with a 1 cm^{-1} resolution, 64 scans were measured and averaged to obtain the final spectra.

Thermogravimetric measurements (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) were performed with a Netzsch STA 449F3 DSC–TGA thermo-balance under synthetic air (25 mL/min). An alumina crucible containing ca. 25 mg of the sample was heated at 5 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ in the 30–700 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature range. Thermogravimetric analysis was also employed to quantify the linker defect degree of UiO-66-NH₂ as detailed in [48]. Figure S2 shows how to fit theoretical weight loss data to a linear equation to calculate experimental defects per formula from thermogravimetric curve weight loss.

2.6. Composite membranes characterisation

The membranes' morphology, pore and fibre size were characterized by scanning electron microscope (SEM, FEI Nova 200). All samples were previously sputtered with a thin layer of gold (Polaron SC502). The mechanical properties of the membranes were evaluated in the tensile more with a load cell of 50 N with a Shimadzu AD-IS universal testing setup. Samples measuring 15 × 10 mm in width were subjected to a stretching process at 1 mm per minute. The O-ES samples were subjected to uniaxial stretching in the direction parallel to the fibers. The samples' thickness was 410 μm for TIPS membranes, 103 μm for ES-NO, and 81 μm for ES-O, respectively, obtained using a Fischer Dualscope MPOR. The stress-strain measurements were conducted in triplicate on both dry and wet samples, with the wet samples being obtained by adding 40 μL of water.

The thermal properties of the samples were assessed using a PerkinElmer 6000 instrument. Approximately 6 mg of samples were introduced into aluminum pans with a volume of 40 μL . Subsequently, the samples were heated from 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 700 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The heating rate employed was 10 $^{\circ}\text{C.min}^{-1}$.

The assessment of surface wettability was conducted using the sessile drop technique with a Data-Physics OCA20 instrument, whereby the contact angle (CA) of 3 μL ultrapure water droplets was measured on all specimens. A total of six measurements were conducted in various zones of the samples. The value is the average contact angle and the corresponding standard deviation.

All samples were subjected to capillary assays. 2.5 cm × 1 cm sample strips were immersed in a vertically oriented green food dye solution. The dye's time to travel 2 cm against gravity was recorded. These tests evaluate how fiber orientation, film porosity, and oxygen plasma treatment affect capillary flow.

2.7. Functional response evaluation

2.7.1. Chromium removal evaluation

The Cr(VI) removal capacity was determined by immersing the prepared CM in a potassium dichromate solution in the dark. The CM were all cut with an area of 1.2 cm^2 to use the smallest membrane area that could be extrapolated to a real environment (later tested on the portable device). A stock solution with a high concentration of Cr(VI) was prepared, from which diluted solutions were successively ready to obtain the calibration curve. Cr(VI) was quantified using the previously reported DPC colorimetric method by UV-Vis spectroscopy (Tecan Infinite M Nano + spectrophotometer) [6,49]. Using a microplate reader and the wavelength range of 450–650 nm, the absorbance variation of the absorption peak at 540 nm of the Cr(VI) UV-Vis spectrum was considered.

All CMs and their controls were placed in a 12-well microplate and immersed in 3 mL of Cr(VI) solution (5 mg/L) under orbital stirring at 200 rpm. Aliquots were removed at predetermined intervals over 300 minutes. The adsorption experiments with the plasma-treated CMs followed the same procedure in batch mode, with decreasing initial Cr (VI) concentrations of 0.75, 1.5, 2.5, and 5 mg/L. Finally, CM was tested in the portable detector device by pouring 400 μL of the solution on the CM to evaluate if it could penetrate the membrane by gravity alone. Different initial doses (0.75, 1.5, 2.5, and 5 mg/L) were tested in tests of 30 and 60 minutes. The chromium adsorption efficiency (E) and capacity (Q_e) were evaluated according to Eqs. 1 and 2:

$$E(\%) = \frac{(C_i - C_f)}{C_i} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$Q_e = \frac{(C_i - C_f)V}{m} \quad (2)$$

where C_f and C_i are the final and initial Cr(VI) concentrations (mg/L), respectively, m is the mass (g) of nano-sorbent into the CM (10 %), and V is the volume (L) of the Cr(VI) contaminated water solution.

Kinetic curves were modelled using non-linear forms of pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order and Elovich kinetic and the intraparticle diffusion model equations [50], referred to as Equations S1 to S4 in the Supplementary Information. In addition, adsorption isotherms were fitted using the Langmuir, Freundlich, Temkin and Dubinin-Radushkevich models, as well as the Polanyi potential, described by Equations S5 to S9 in the Supplementary Information [51].

2.7.2. Portable sensor evaluation

The calibration curves were established by measuring Cr(VI)

concentrations at 0.5, 1, 2.5, and 5 parts per million (ppm). Using a micropipette, 1 mL of each concentration was vertically deposited on the membranes, allowing them to pass through them. The Cr(VI) was trapped in the membrane while the remaining filtered solution was collected in the portable system's reservoir. Following this step, the Cr(VI) presented in the filtrated solution was quantified using the colorimetric method described in Section 2.3. The chromium retained on the membrane was complexed with DPC to develop the solid matrix's colour further. To this end, 20 μL of DPC reagent was dropped at the membrane, and the absorbance was recorded at 540 nm.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physical chemical characterization of the metal organic frameworks

After the synthesis, washing and activation process of UiO-66-NH₂ sample (this process generally involves the elimination of guest molecules, such as solvents and water, from the pores in order to provide the active sites available for adsorption) was characterized by XRD, IR TGA-DSC and SEM techniques. The x-ray diffraction pattern confirms that the sample has an excellent crystallinity. The data is in agreement with previous works, and the simulated pattern was obtained from the crystallographic information file. In addition, the full profile matching analysis of the data (Fig. 2a) discards the presence of additional impurities and further confirms the fitting of the diffraction maxima with the ones expected from the crystallographic cell and the space group of the UiO-66-NH₂ material. IR-spectra were recorded in as-synthesised samples after activating it at 150 °C (Fig. 2b). Post-activation IR analysis guarantees the removal of absorbed impurities and the evaluation of the dehydration/solvation process of water, solvent, or species that modulate bonds by coordinating with the metal ions of the structure. It also allows the evaluation of the thermal stability of the MOF structure. It

provides an understanding of how heat treatment can affect the functional groups and overall performance of MOFs in adsorption applications [52]. The interval from 2000 to 600 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra shows many of the vibrational modes associated with the organic linker. In detail, from 1650 to 1350 cm^{-1} the absorption bands associated to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrational modes of COO⁻ groups are found. At higher values ($\sim 1700 - 1710 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), a weak band ascribed to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ vibrational mode is found. This signature confirms the presence of uncoordinated carboxyl groups and defective positions within the network. Additional bands, such as the symmetric (i.e. 1050–1020 cm^{-1}) and asymmetric (i.e. 970–950 cm^{-1}) δ vibration of C-H bonds, are also observed. It is important to stress at this point, that the vibrational modes arising from N-H bonds of amino groups can be found in the low energy region (3500–3300 cm^{-1}) as two weak signals only after fully dehydrating/de-solvating the compounds at high temperatures, as detailed in the ex-situ IR-spectra acquired after heating the samples at different temperatures (Fig. 2b). In addition to the vibrations associated with the amino-terephthalate organic units, it is also interesting to highlight the bands arising from the inorganic blocks, with the Zr-O stretching ascribed to the signal at 660 cm^{-1} . Indeed, this band and the one at 760 cm^{-1} show a significant shift when the IR spectra are recorded after heating the materials at 150 °C for 30 min. Thermogravimetric data show the typical data for UiO-66-NH₂ material. (Fig. 2c). A first weight loss, associated with the solvent release, occurs between 30 °C and 150 °C. A second weight loss is observed between the initial solvent lost and the final linker calcination steps (i.e. between 150 and 350 °C), related to the zirconium clusters' dehydration process. The last step, above 350–400 °C and until 600°C, is related to the organic linker calcination leading to a final zirconium oxide residue after the measurement. In this last process, if the weight value at 350 °C is normalized to 100 %, the linker defects of UiO-66-NH₂ can be calculated as detailed in the supplementary file (Figure S1).

Fig. 2. a) X-ray diffraction pattern of the UiO-66-NH₂ sample b) IR-spectra of the UiO-66-NH₂ as-synthesised samples, and after activating it at 150 °C. c) Thermogravimetric of the UiO-66-NH₂. d) Scanning electron microscopy images of the MOF crystallized as single crystals with octahedral geometries.

In detail, UiO-66-NH₂ shows approximately 1.4 linkers missing per formula unit. Thus, the material is close to the maximum threshold (i.e. 2.0) above which the framework begins to destabilize. The quantification of the defective sites is important when applying chromium adsorption since these sites are preferential positions for the coordinative immobilization of the chromate anions within the framework of UiO-66-NH₂. Finally, scanning electron microscopy images show that the MOF crystallized as single crystals with octahedral geometries (Fig. 2d). The particle size distribution is relatively narrow, with a mean diameter of 325 nm.

3.2. Physical-chemical characterization of composite membranes

3.2.1. Morphology of the membranes

To validate their expected morphologies and ascertain their porosity, the PVDF-HFP and PVDF-HP@MOF composite membranes (CM) must be systematically characterized. Fig. 3 displays representative SEM images of the membranes prepared by TIPS and ES methods.

The SEM images show that the gradual solvent evaporation during the TIPS process leads to the development of a uniformly distributed porous structure at the micro-scale (Fig. 3 a-d), as expected for PVDF-

HFP TIPS membranes [44]. The addition of MOF nanoparticles causes a slight alteration in the microstructure of the membrane, with the PVDF-HFP@MOF membranes showing a narrower and more compact structure (Fig. 3c). The inclusion of MOFs alters the viscosity of the PVDF-HFP solution employed for the membrane casting and, therefore, the formation of pores during the solvent evaporation process. In addition, the MOF nanoparticles may disrupt the polymer crystallization and solvent evaporation, resulting in a pore structure that is more tightly packed and compact [53].

Regarding the plasma-treated TIPS membranes (Fig. 3b and Fig. 3d), SEM indicates a subtle alteration in their morphology compared to the untreated counterparts. A certain degree of melting of the membrane gives rise to an alteration in the morphology of the pores if observed after plasma application. This alteration is attributed to the localised melting of the polymer, caused by the high power (100 W) and prolonged exposure time (10 min) to the plasma.

The membranes produced by electrospinning have fibres exhibiting dimensions in the micrometer range, as measured by ImageJ software. An average width of approximately $3.1 \pm 1.7 \mu\text{m}$ has been calculated for the randomly oriented fibers and of $1.9 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{m}$ for oriented fibers. Compared to the randomly oriented fibers, the oriented homologues are

Fig. 3. Representative SEM images of the different processed membranes a) TIPS PVDF-HFP membrane; b) TIPS PVDF-HFP membrane with O₂ plasma; c) TIPS PVDF-HFP/MOF membrane; d) TIPS PVDF-HFP/MOF membrane with O₂ plasma, f) Randomly oriented PVDF-HFP electrospun fibers Randomly oriented PVDF-HFP electrospun with O₂ plasma; e) Randomly oriented PVDF-HFP/MOFs electrospun fibers; f) PVDF-HFP/MOFs electrospun fibers with O₂ plasma; g) Oriented PVDF-HFP electrospun fibers; h) Oriented PVDF-HFP electrospun fibers with O₂ plasma; i) Oriented PVDF-HFP/MOFs electrospun fibers; j) Oriented PVDF-HFP/MOFs electrospun fibers with O₂ plasma.

more uniform in diameter throughout their lengths. Overall, membranes with a smoother surface are generated due to their oriented deposition. [46]. Introducing the MOF nanoparticles into the ES membranes does not alter the fibres' dimension, orientation, and distribution (Figs. 3j and 3 m). However, some clusters within the samples have been detected. Plasma treatment induces melting of the adjacent fibres.

3.2.2. Spectroscopic and thermal properties of the membranes

The polymeric crystalline phases of PVDF-HFP were identified using FTIR-ATR spectroscopy (Fig. 4a-c). The FTIR spectra of PVDF-HFP displayed the distinctive absorption bands corresponding to the skeleton bending of C(F)-C(H)-C(F), symmetrical stretching of C-C and F-C-F and stretching of C-F at wavenumbers of 875, 1072, 1169, and 1404 cm^{-1} , respectively. In MOF-loaded membranes, three additional weak signals corresponding to the vibrational modes of the organic linkers were detected (i.e. 747, 1598, and 1659 cm^{-1}). The FTIR spectra of the samples exposed and unexposed to plasma show no relevant differences. This evidence indicates that O_2 plasma does not induce any significant chemical change [46].

The thermal properties are evaluated by TGA (Fig. 4d-f). The thermal degradation of the PVDF-HFP matrix involves two concurrent weight losses occurring between 425 and 450 $^\circ\text{C}$ and between 450 and 550 $^\circ\text{C}$. These weight losses are predominantly caused by breaking carbon-hydrogen (C-H) bonds. This occurs because the bond strength of C-H (410 kJ mol^{-1}) is lower compared to that of C-F (460 kJ mol^{-1}) [54]. Furthermore, the weight loss rate during the initial phase of heat degradation is lower for the composite samples. This phenomenon also occurs for PVDF composites with different inorganic and organic fillers [55-57].

It is noticed that oxygen plasma treatment reduces the degradation temperature of pristine TIPS and of OF and ROF electrospun membranes. In these cases, the TGA curves demonstrate a distinct shift for the plasma-treated samples in comparison to the untreated ones. Plasma treatment introduces hydrophilic groups (i.e. carbonyl, carboxyl, or hydroxyl) onto the polymer surface, which in turn induces a decrease in the thermal stability of the membrane [58].

In relation to CM containing MOF nanoparticles, a further decrease

in their degradation temperature is also observed when treated with plasma. This shift provides evidence of a combined effect on the thermal stability due to the presence of filler-nanoparticles in the polymeric matrix and a surface chemistry alteration arising from plasma treatment. It is still unclear whether the plasma can expose or even damage the MOF particles [59]. This is unlikely to occur considering the local temperatures achieved during plasma treatment and the thermal stability (i.e. 350 – 400 $^\circ\text{C}$) of UiO-66- NH_2 [60]. However, with the plasma treatment and insertion of polar functional groups, characterized by an abundance of unpaired electrons, have the potential to substantially decrease the thermal stability of the UiO-66- NH_2 . This phenomenon occurs because these groups can influence the distribution of electric charge and the electronegativity inside the structure of the MOF, reducing the strength of the binding between the metal and oxygen [59].

3.2.3. Mechanical, wettability, and permeability characteristics of the membranes

Stress-strain mechanical assays were conducted on dry and wet plasma-treated membranes. The stress-strain mechanical curves show thermoplastic characteristics with a linear elastic response before yielding and a plastic regime after yielding in which the material deforms permanently with load or stress. Hooke's law was used to calculate each sample's Young's modulus from the linear regime of stress-strain curves [61]. Fig. 5a-b present the characteristic stress-strain curves up to 10 % of strain, along with the Young's modulus of the samples under study.

Regardless of the MOF content, the stress-strain curves exhibited by all the plasma-treated membranes display characteristic properties of thermoplastic materials. Furthermore, when examining Young's modulus, it becomes evident that the morphology, condition (dry or wet) and the addition of MOFs further impact their mechanical properties [62]. The porous membranes obtained by TIPS are characterized by the lowest Young's modulus values (i.e. 90.1 ± 4.3 and 82.7 ± 3.4 MPa for dry and wet membranes, respectively). Concerning the electrospun membranes, the alignment of the fibres improves Young's modulus, increasing its value from 102.1 ± 5.2 in non-aligned membranes to 189.5 ± 6.9 MPa in aligned counterparts when the membranes are in a dry

Fig. 4. a) Representative FTIR-ATR spectra of the PVDF-HFP TIPS; b) electrospun PVDF-HFP OF membranes; c) electrospun PVDF-HFP ROF membranes. d) TGA curves of PVDF-HFP TIPS membranes; e) electrospun PVDF-HFP OF membranes; and f) electrospun PVDF-HFP ROF membranes.

Fig. 5. a) Representative stress-strain mechanical curves up to 10 % of strain and b) the corresponding Young's moduli mean value and standard deviation for the different membranes in dry and wet conditions.

state. A similar tendency is observed for wet conditions, with Young's modulus of 78.9 ± 2.6 and 171.3 ± 5.9 MPa for membranes showing random and oriented fibers [61]. Although the morphology of the membranes is the main factor governing their mechanical response, the addition of MOFs slightly decrease their mechanical properties. It is well known that the addition of fillers to PVDF-HFP matrices can act either as a defect or a reinforcing agent depending on filler-polymer interactions and filler aggregation state [63,64].

The hydrophobicity of PVDF-HFP can represent a drawback for water remediation applications. In addition, for composite systems based on PVDF-HFP and MOFs, significant encapsulation of the MOF particles within the polymer matrix is usually observed. The composite systems' structuration limits their effective contact with the target substance to capture or sense pollutants. Various approaches have been explored to tune the wettability of PVDF-HFP-based membranes, including plasma treatment, defluorination-sulfonation, surface coating/deposition, blending, and electron beam radiation exposition [65]. Plasma treatment is one of the most appealing approaches since it preserves the polymer's main physicochemical features while increasing its hydrophilicity. In our case study, this surface chemistry modification was proved by contact angle measurements. The water contact angle

values of the PVDF-HFP samples, both before and after plasma treatment, allow the evaluation of the wetting characteristics of the membranes quantitatively (Fig. 6-a).

The results show that the structure of the treated samples directly influences the resulting contact angle and, consequently, the surface's ability to be wetted. Untreated PVDF-HFP porous membranes obtained by TIPS show contact angle values (CA) of $94.1 \pm 4.5^\circ$, indicating a more hydrophilic nature than fiber-based membranes. The fiber-based membranes show higher contact angles of $114.7 \pm 3.5^\circ$ and $105.9 \pm 3.9^\circ$ for the RO- and O-PVDF-HFP membranes, respectively. The observed results are attributed to TIPS, OF and ROS membranes showing different uniformity, roughness and porosity of their surface, which slightly affect their wettability. TIPS membranes tend to have lower contact angles (indicating higher hydrophilicity) due to their porous surface, while electrospun fibers tend to have higher angles (indicating higher hydrophobicity) [66].

The inclusion of MOF nanoparticles into the membranes results in an enhancement of their hydrophilicity that lowers their contact angle ($76.8 \pm 4.1^\circ$ for pore-based membranes, $95.7 \pm 3.9^\circ$ for RO-ES and $91.2 \pm 3.1^\circ$ for O-ES membranes). This is related to the hydrophilic nature of UiO-66-NH₂ [67]. However, the parameter that makes the difference in

Fig. 6. a) Contact angle and b) capillary flow rates in the "antigravity" direction of a dye solution for the different membranes before and after oxygen plasma treatment.

improving the wettability of the PVDF-HFP membranes is the plasma treatment. The values of CA of all samples treated with O₂ plasma dropped to 0°, indicating total absorption of the water drop after a 30-second exposure. The generation of C-O and C=O functional groups [68] in the surface of the membranes after their exposure to plasma is the main factor explaining these experimental findings.

Capillary flow rate tests were conducted to assess the ability of the manufactured membranes to generate passive flow. The results are

shown in Fig. 6-b. Plasma-treated RO-ES membranes are characterized by capillary flow rates of $39.5 \pm 2.9 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$. The rate significantly increases when using plasma-treated O-ES membranes, reaching values of $82.6 \pm 4.2 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$. This demonstrates that the orientation of the fibers is an essential factor to consider in enhancing the capillary flows. The orientation of the fibres along the flow readily accounts for this outcome. The plasma-treated TIPS membranes exhibit capillary flow rates of $44.8 \pm 3.7 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, a value in the mid-term between the

Fig. 7. Adsorption capacity of Cr(VI) (5 mg/L) after 300 minutes by a) TIPS membranes, with plasma treatment (TIPS-P), MOFs (10 %-TIPS) and MOF and plasma treatment (10 %-TIPS-P). c) Oriented fibers membranes: OF, OF-P, 10 %OF-P; and in d) non-oriented fibers membranes: ROF, 10 %ROF, ROF-P and 10 %ROF-P. Adsorption capacity of Cr(VI) (0.75, 1.5, 2.5, 5 mg/L) of plasma treated (P) b) TIPS Membrane and 10 %TIPS, d) Oriented-Fibers membranes (OF) and 10 %OF and f) Randomly-Oriented Fibers membranes and 10 %ROF, for 300 minutes under orbital stirring.

studied samples. Therefore, the rate at which plasma-treated PVDF-HFP membranes allow capillary flow can be adjusted by modifying their morphology or the alignment of the fibers [46]. The capillary flow values of the composite membranes are slightly increased compared to the pristine polymer samples due to the adsorption of water molecules by the hydrophilic effect of the MOF particles dispersed inside the membrane structures.

3.3. Functional characterization of the membranes

3.3.1. Chromium adsorption

The composites' functional characterisation was evaluated by their efficiency and mass capacity of adsorption over hexavalent chromium in solution. The membranes (~6 mg) were exposed to 3 mL of a 5 mg/L Cr(VI) solution for 300 minutes under orbital agitation. Aliquots were taken at different time intervals during the exposure. A comparative analysis of the influence of the morphologies of TIPS, OF and ROF polymeric and MOF-composite membranes before and after plasma treatment was performed. Fig. 7 summarizes two phases of the study: first, the Cr(VI) adsorption capacity of the different membrane morphologies is shown with and without plasma treatment (Fig. 7-a,c and e) at the same experimental conditions over 300 minutes. Based on these initial results, the membranes that demonstrated the most promising performance were subjected to an adsorption study at Cr(VI) concentrations ranging from 5 ppm to 0.75 ppm (Fig. 7-b,d and f) to assess their efficiency at varying contamination levels.

The TIPS and 10 %TIPS membranes exhibited adsorption efficiencies of 5.07 % and 1.96 %, respectively. In contrast, after the plasma treatment, the membranes showed significantly higher adsorption of 9.68 % and 74.10 % (with Q_e values of 0.03 mg/g and 0.70 mg/g), as displayed in Fig. 7-a and Table S1. Compared to pristine membranes, incorporating MOF particles (10 %TIPS) results in lower removal efficiencies, although this difference is relatively small. MOFs promoted topography changes on the membrane surface, as can be observed in the SEM images (Figs. 3-a and 3-c), where there is a reduction in pores, resulting in a surface that is less favourable for water percolation, consequently reducing the Cr(VI) adsorption capacity. Similarly, the OF and 10 %OF membranes showed very low affinity and capacity to capture Cr(VI) (i.e. 0.63 % and 0.00 %). The performance is greatly improved to 4.06 % and 98.85 % (with Q_e values of 0.12 mg/g and 2.32 mg/g) after the plasma treatment (Fig. 7-c). A similar trend is found for ROF and 10 %ROF membranes (i.e. 1.24 and 0.00 %, respectively), with a subsequent increase to 9.04 and 76.39 % after plasma treatment, as illustrated in Fig. 7-e.

These results show that MOF particles are significantly encapsulated within the PVDF-HFP matrix, preventing their active role as Cr(VI) sorbent, regardless of the morphology of the membrane. Surface modification through plasma treatment is an effective strategy for enhancing adsorption efficiency, especially in MOF-composite systems. Incorporating hydrophilic carbonyl groups into PVDF-HFP membranes not only increases the water permeability but generates hydrophilic chemical groups able to work as adsorption sites for hexavalent chromium [46]. In addition, plasma treatment enhances the Cr(VI) adsorption for MOF-composite systems by a factor of ten. Given the promising performance of plasma-treated compounds in Cr(VI) adsorption, further experiments were performed in those samples. The initial concentration of Cr(VI) was modified to evaluate its effect on the adsorption capability, and the adsorption kinetics of plasma-treated membranes were systematically assessed at four distinct concentrations, 5, 2.5, 1.5 and 0.75 ppm, over 300 minutes. Pristine PVDF-HFP membranes were used as a reference.

In these evaluations, the contribution of pristine PVDF-HFP membranes that lack plasma treatment shows deficient, near negligible, adsorption capacity for chromate anions, with a maximum Q_e value of 0.12 mg/g for OF-P ([Cr]=5 ppm). Incorporating MOF particles into the membranes significantly improves the adsorption efficiency of fibre-

based (10 %OF-P and 10 %ROF-P) and TIPS membranes (10 %TIPS-P). In contrast to the pristine polymeric membranes, for MOF-based membranes, there is a clear correlation between the adsorption capacity and the Cr(VI) concentration (Figs. 7-b), 7-d), and 7-f). Still, the capacity values obtained for membranes processed by different routes differ significantly. In detail, at a concentration of 5 ppm of Cr(VI), the maximum Q_e values reached were 2.32 mg/g, 1.86 mg/g, and 0.70 mg/g for 10 %OF-P, 10 %ROF-P, and 10 %TIPS-P CM, respectively. The corresponding adsorption efficiency values were 98.85 %, 76.39 %, and 74.10 % (Table S2). If the MOF in 10 %OF-P is fully accessible, 24 and 26 % encapsulation degrees can be calculated for MOF nanoparticles in 10 %ROF-P, and 10 %TIPS-P CM, respectively. The 10 %OF-P membranes are more efficient for Cr(VI) adsorption than 10 %TIPS-P and 10 %ROF membranes due to their higher surface area and better alignment, leading to a reduction of the MOF particles encapsulation, and to a higher access to adsorption active sites for chromate anions. Additionally, their oriented fibers have smaller inter-fiber spaces, enhancing Cr(VI) uptake. All of these characteristics are mirrored in the adsorption kinetics and adsorption capacity of the membranes, as detailed in the fittings of the experimental data to different models reported in the Figures S2 and S3, and Tables S3 and S4. The best match of the kinetics and isotherms of adsorption are obtained for a pseudo second order kinetic and Langmuir isotherms models. This evidence indicates that the kinetics of the chromate uptake is partially hindered by the PVDF hydrophobic matrix, and in parallel, that the adsorption mechanism is based on a mono-layer uptake of chromate anions at the surface of the pores walls, and specifically at the linker defective sites and ammonium groups of the MOF framework

The processing route of membranes by TIPS or electrospinning and their postprocessing by plasma modulate the encapsulation degree of the MOF nanoparticles, and, hence, the performance of the final system, as illustrated in Fig. 8a.1. For TIPS, the membranes have well interconnected and non-interconnected pores where both the active and encapsulated MOF nanoparticles are located (Fig. 8a.1). As the plasma treatment only affects the surface of these thick membranes, the de-encapsulation of MOF nanoparticles is limited to their surface (Fig. 8a.1). Thus, the adsorption capacity increase is limited (Fig. 8a.2). Contrary, in OF and FOR membranes, the fibers, and the membrane itself, are thin enough to be affected in a great extent for the plasma treatment (Fig. 8a.1). Thus, the exposure of the MOF nanoparticles is more effective leading to better adsorption performances (Fig. 8a.2).

Regarding the mechanistic aspects of chromium detection, the complexation mechanism between the DPC and the hexavalent chromium must be considered. As illustrated in Fig. 8b.1, the chromate oxyanions in acidic conditions are reduced to trivalent chromium in the presence of DPC. The diphenylcarbazide (DPC) reagent is transformed into diphenylcarbazone (DPCA) that coordinates the Cr^{III} ions to form the $[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}(\text{DPCA})_2]^+$ complex. In parallel, the chromium capture in UiO-66-NH₂ variants and its complexation have been studied previously [24, 36,69,70]. In general terms, when a Cr(VI) solution with low concentrations (< 5 ppm) is employed during adsorption, chromate anions are adsorbed as isolated species in (I) the linker defective positions near the Zr₆ clusters or (II) by electrostatically driven adsorption close to the ammonium protonated groups (Fig. 8b.2). As reported previously, the UiO-66-NH₂ variants have as well some capacity to reduce the immobilized Cr(VI) into Cr(III) species [70] (Fig. 8b.3). Regardless the oxidation state of chromium stabilized within the MOF, the reduction and complexation of hexavalent chromium, or the direct complexation of trivalent species by DPCA, would induce a similar color development than the one observed in the liquid state (Fig. 8b.4). Steric impediments could indeed limit the access for some chromium ions to the DPCA molecules that form the complex. Nevertheless, the similarities of the colors obtained in the membranes and the ones developed in the solution point towards a similar Cr-DPCA stabilization within the MOF structure (Fig. 8b.4)

Fig. 9. a) Schematic 3D representation of the portable filtration and detection system for Cr(VI) and the different morphologies of the multifunctional membranes; b) Adsorption efficiencies of Cr(VI) (0.5, 1, 2.5, 5 mg/L) by oriented membranes (10 %OF-P) inserted in the portable device at different adsorption times (0, 30 and 60 mins); c) Colorimetric calibration curves of different Cr(VI) concentrations. The results are presented as mean grey values and corresponding standard deviation, using ImageJ software, of measurements performed in the reaction chambers of the microfluidic substrates; d) Representative images of the portable device and the tested membranes after Cr(VI) assays.

4. Conclusions

The structure and porosity of poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) and Metal-Organic Framework (UiO-66-NH₂) composite membranes were tuned by their processing methods such as TIPS and randomly oriented and oriented electrospun fibers. Plasma treatment was applied to improve the hydrophilicity and reduce the encapsulation degree of the MOF nanoparticles into the polymeric scaffolds. The membranes' physicochemical properties and capillary flow rates were fully analyzed, later to correlate them with their hexavalent chromium adsorption efficiency. The most effective morphology was then integrated into the 3D-printed portable system and tested for adsorption and sensing of chromate anions.

In general terms, the plasma treatment increases the exposure of the MOF nanoparticles to the solution, but it induces a partial melting of the polymeric matrix, especially for random and oriented fibers membranes. It is evidenced that the morphology, condition (dry or wet) and the integration of MOF nanoparticles into the polymeric scaffold directly impact the mechanical properties of composite membranes. Nonetheless, all membranes still show appropriate mechanical properties.

Regarding Cr(VI) adsorption capacity by the membranes MOFs are the active component, especially in plasma-treated oriented (10 %OF-P) and randomly oriented (10 %ROF-P) fibers, with efficiency values of 98.85 % for 10 %OF-P. This electrospun membrane, integrated into the portable system, achieved adsorption rates of 49.8 % in 60 minutes for a 5 ppm – 1 mL Cr(VI) solution. The complexation of chromium anions by diphenylcarbazide in the MOF composite membranes positively correlates with the Cr(VI) concentration in the liquid phase, confirmed by the

absorbance in solution (R^2 of 0.99).

This work represents an essential step toward developing portable and simple-to-operate technology for the simultaneous removal and sensing of Cr(VI) from different water matrixes. It is important to note that further tuning of the preconcentration conditions of chromate in the membrane could open the avenue to lower the detection limit explored in this work (i.e., 0.5 ppm) below the legal limit established by the environmental monitoring agencies (i.e. ≤ 0.1 ppm). From this point, it would be interesting to assess the recyclability and reusability of the outperforming membranes and confirm the cost-effectiveness of their use. Additionally, non-fluorinated membranes, such as those made from biodegradable polymers as polylactic acid, chitosan or poly(D,L-lactide-co-glycolide acid) can also be evaluated, to provide environmentally safer and fully sustainable water remediation solutions.

Author contributions

The manuscript was written with contributions from all authors. All authors have approved the final version of the manuscript.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Joana M. Queirós: Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Leire Celaya-Azcoaga:** Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Roberto Fernández de Luiz:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Pedro Martins:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software,

Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Senentxu Lanceros-Mendez:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Ricardo Brito-Pereira:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) under strategic funding PTDC/03781/2022 and UIDB/04650/2020. The authors also thank the FCT for financial support under grant UMINHO/BIPD/2023/16 (R.B.P.) and 2021.08822.BD (J. M.Q.), and the contract DOI 10.54499/2020.02802.CEECIND/CP1600/CT0017. This study formed part of the Advanced Materials programme and was supported by MCIN with funding from European Union Next-GenerationEU (PRTR-C17.I1) and the IKUR Strategy of the Department of Education of the Basque Government. The authors thank the financial support as well from the Spanish Agencia Estatal de Investigación (AEI) through EVOLMOF PID2021-1229400B-C31 (AEI/FEDER, UE) (including FEDER financial support), ENZYMOF (TED2021-130621B-C42) and “TailingR32Green” ERA-MIN3 No.101003575, Grant PCI2022-132983 funded by MCIN/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033 and by the “European Union NextGeneration EU/PRTR. Funding by the Basque Government Industry Departments under the ELKARTEK and PIBA-2022-1-0032 programs is also acknowledged. The MSCA-RISE-2017 (No 778412) INDESMOF HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01-01 SELF-AQUASENS (101131379), which received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe research and innovation programmes, are also acknowledged programs and is also acknowledged. Technical and human support provided by SGiker (UPV/EHU, MICINN, GV/EJ, EGEF and ESF) is gratefully acknowledged. The authors thank Dr. J. Borges and Prof. F. Vaz for experimental support with the plasma treatment.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jece.2024.113839](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2024.113839).

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